

Example Data Management Plan – complete version with full responses

The role of the *Drosophila scarface* gene in feeding behaviour

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Complete version with full responses

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Based on

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(Q1) Proposal name

The role of the *Drosophila scarface* gene in feeding behaviour

(Q2) Description of the data: Type of study

The aim of this study is to elucidate the role of the serine protease homolog *scarface* in the regulation of feeding behaviour. Quantitative feeding behavioural data will be collected in *scarface* classical mutants (*scaf27*), *scarface* overexpression and *scarface* knock-down flies and compared to wild-type flies.

(Q3) Description of the data: Types of data

The project will create non-human (*Drosophila melanogaster*) data exclusively. The data will consist of:

- **Volumes of food consumed**
 - **Capillary feeder (CAFE) assay:** The volume of food ingested will be recorded by measuring the food remaining in a glass capillary after varying feeding times (3h - 24h). The length of the food column remaining in the capillary will be measured using digital callipers and noted down in lab books. The data will be digitized and stored as tab separated values (CSV) and will include genotype, food type, replicate number and volume of food consumed
 - **Dye ingestion assay:** The volume of dye-labelled food ingested will be recorded by measuring the dye concentration in homogenized flies using a spectrophotometer. Spectrophotometer readings will be saved as CSV and annotated with genotype, food type and replicate number. Food volumes will be calculated from the absorbance values using a standard curve and this data will be added to the CSV file
- **Outcomes of binary food choice assays:** will be collected as tab separated values and consist of genotype, food choice 1, food choice 2, replicate number, number of flies on each food and preference index, calculated as $(\text{Number of flies eating food 1}) - (\text{Number of flies eating food 2}) / (\text{Number of flies eating food 1}) + (\text{Number of flies eating food 2})$.

(Q4) Description of the data: Origin of the data

The study will generate original primary data.

(Q5) Description of the data: Format and scale of the data

Each assay will be performed on four genotypes: CantonS (wild-type), scarface classical mutants (scf27), scarface overexpression and scarface knock-down flies. Each assay will be performed in quadruplicate and on a minimum of 20 flies per replicate. All data will be stored as CSV. The total size of the data will not exceed 100MB

(Q6) Managing, storing and curating data

Data will be stored on local hard drives with synchronous replication to cloud storage (Google Drive). All data will be stored within a project folder containing sub-folders for CAFE, dye and binary choice experiments. Data file names will be stereotyped and contain date, assay and a reference number to an entry in the electronic lab book containing all relevant metadata.

(Q7) Metadata standards and data documentation

Biological metadata (organism, strain, developmental stage, sex, tissue and genotype) will be stored in Experimental Factor Ontology (EFO) (format ebi.ac.uk/efo/).

Diet composition will be stored in Compositional Dietary Nutrition Ontology (CDNO) format (ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/cdno).

Fly genotypes will be stored in Flybase stock ontology (wiki.flybase.org/wiki/FlyBase:Controlled_vocabularies_used_by_FlyBase).

(Q8) Data preservation strategy and standards

All research data will be kept locally for a minimum of 10 years after the end of the project.

Raw data and associated metadata will be preserved longer-term by publishing it as supplemental data to a research paper describing the results, or through publication of a dedicated data publication, for example, in Zenodo (zenodo.org).

(Q9) Where will data be shared?

Raw data and associated metadata will be preserved longer-term by publishing it as supplemental data to a research paper describing the results, or through publication of a dedicated data publication, for example, in Zenodo (zenodo.org).

(Q10) When will data be available?

All data will be made available upon publication or within three years of generation of the dataset, whichever comes first.

(Q11) How will data be made findable and accessible?

Raw data and associated metadata will be published as supplemental data to a research paper describing the results, or through publication of a dedicated data publication, for example, in Zenodo (zenodo.org). In the latter case, the Digital Object Identifier pointing to the data publication will be included in all subsequent papers that make use of this data.

(Q12) How will data be made reusable?

The data will be accompanied by rich metadata. Where possible, this metadata will be organised using existing ontologies (see Q7), complemented with additional free text descriptions of the data.

(Q13) Restrictions or delays to sharing, with planned actions to limit such restrictions

No human, sensitive, proprietary or patentable data will be produced or used in this study. We do not foresee any restrictions or delays in data sharing.

(Q14) Secondary use

Researchers studying molecular determinants of feeding behaviour could benefit from this data.

(Q15) Formal information/data security standards

The University is ISO 27001 certified.

(Q16) Main risks to data security

Only model organism data will be generated.

(Q17) Capabilities

The university provides unlimited storage capacity on Google Drive as well as access to Arkivum for long term storage of large datasets.

Furthermore, the university provides a free platform to share the intellectual product of the university freely and openly with the staff and students of the university or with the global academic and public community (RADAR).

(Q18) Maintaining and implementing the Data Management Plan

The data management plan will be updated throughout the life-time of the project. Data management plan implementation, auditing and revision is the responsibility of the PI and will be a recurring topic during the weekly team meetings.

(Q19) Environmental considerations

Environmental sustainability at the University is guided by the framework of our externally certified ISO14001:2015 Environmental Management System (EMS). The EMS enforces an environmental policy that sets out our principles and goals, and is supported by a series of strategies outlining our key vision, drivers and objectives for each key aspect of environmental sustainability. The university also takes part in the LEAF initiative to reduce the carbon emissions of research labs and create an environment that supports research quality

(Q20) Responsibilities

Person responsible for:

- **Study-wide data management:** PI
- **Metadata creation:** Unnamed PDRA (new hire for this project)
- **Data security:** PI
- **Quality assurance of data:** PI and University Research Data Manager